

Enhancing forage productivity by grass legume intercropping for sustainable dairy farming

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Livestock farming is the backbone of Indian agriculture and is critical to employment generation, particularly in rural regions. Fodders are distinct from food and commercial crops in that they are planted primarily for the fresh green vegetative biomass. The feed supply situation in India is exceedingly fragile, with a large shortfall. India has 37.28 % of the world's cattle population (Sonavale *et al.*, 2020), putting significant demand on available feed and fodder, especially as area accessible for fodder cultivation has been shrinking. A lack of feed supplies has frequently been identified as a primary explanation for Kerala's dramatic fall in cattle numbers during the previous two decades. In India, there is no practice of fodder cultivation in rural regions, and animals consume naturally occurring grasses and bushes that are poor in protein and low calories. They are so largely reliant on seasonal changes, which causes fluctuations in fodder availability, which affects milk production throughout the year and eventually leads to financial crises among dairy producers. So here comes the role of a grass legume mixture as a balanced fodder supply that meet the daily requirement of roughage in the diet.

Hybrid Napier is a fodder grass that has found appeal among dairy producers. In comparison to other grasses, this grass is highly suited to Kerala's agro-climatic conditions due to its rapid growth, shade tolerance, palatability, high nutritional quality, and herbage output (Savitha *et al.*, 2012). Several studies suggest that grass-legume mixtures are good for long-term land production. Apart from providing high protein feed for animals, legumes can improve soil health by increasing organic matter, nitrogen fixation, phosphorous solubilization and improving soil physical properties and microbial activity (Ghosh *et al.*, 2007). Planting grass-legume combinations may be a viable alternative for improving soil health and increasing fodder yield, nutritional value and net farm profit in a hay production system (Dhakal and Islam, 2018).

According to Lakshmi *et al.* (2002), cowpea was the best intercrop for Hybrid Napier among the annual fodder legumes. According to Verma *et al.* (2011), Hybrid Napier intercropped with cowpea generated the maximum green fodder production of 262.3 t/ha. Alaladae *et al.* (2013) found that intercropping guinea grass (*Panicum maximum*) with Caribbean stylo (*Stylosanthes hamata*) improved biomass output. Intercropping fodder maize with lablab bean improved crude protein content while decreasing crude fibre content (Khogali *et al.*, 2011). When grown as sole crops, pearl millet had a low protein content and sesbania had a low fibre and ash content, however in intercropping systems protein, fibre, and ash contents of the fodder combination improved (Rasool *et al.*, 2017). The inclusion of a legume in Napier grass-based diet has been shown to improve animal performance in terms of milk production because of its high nutrient content. Grass - legume mixtures yielded as much or more dry matter than grasses alone and showed better seasonal distribution of forage production than grasses alone, and it also improves the soil physical properties.

At the present time, the country is facing a net deficit of 61.1 percent in green fodder, 21.9 percent in dry crop residues, and 64 percent in concentrate feeds due to a limited area under fodder production, namely 4% in cultivable fodder production and 3.5% in grazing land of the total geographical area, which is insufficient to meet the demand of a growing animal population (Dhananjay, 2013). As a result, there is an urgent need to seek for alternative fodder options that are both sustainable in nature and capable of covering our fodder shortfall so a fodder legume intercrop mix may assist farmers in obtaining a highly nutritious feed, allowing them to lessen their reliance on concentrates.

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